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Historical Ontology of Urban Space project

The Urbanonto System. User Guide

Warsaw 2021

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<https://urbanonto.ihpan.edu.pl/>

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Architecture

The Urbanonto System is made up of three basic components:

1. the ontological component
2. the database component
3. the data presentation component:
 - a. Geoserver
 - b. RDF triple store

The function of the ontological component is to formulate the domains of the Urbanonto project as specifications compliant with the semantic technology recommended by W3C.

The function of the database component is to prepare geohistorical data by using the data available in the ontology. The function of the data presentation component is to make available the data collected under the project.

III. 1 System architecture

A more detailed description of system architecture is available in the project repository at <https://github.com/urbanonto>.

Ontology

What is it?

The Urbanonto Ontology is an [OWL ontology](#) stored in [Turtle](#) serialization. It is a domain ontology, which aims to conceptualize the history of the topographic objects which make up an urban centre, as depicted in traditional topographic maps.

In the Urbanonto system, ontology serves a two-fold, purpose. It serves as:

1. a glossary of terms connected with urban representation
2. a resource containing the data used in the database:
 - a. list of topographic object types
 - b. list of functions

The Urbanonto Ontology makes direct use (meaning [owl:import](#)) of two additional ontologies:

1. BDOT10k ontology
2. ontoghis ontology

The screenshot shows a web browser window with the URL `http://purl.org/urbanonto`. The page title is "urbanonto (http://purl.org/urbanonto)". The browser tabs include "Active ontology", "Entities", "Individuals by class", and "DL Query". The main content area is titled "Ontology header:" and contains the following information:

- Ontology IRI:** `http://purl.org/urbanonto`
- Ontology Version IRI:** e.g. `http://purl.org/urbanonto/1.0.0`
- Annotations:**
 - `rdfs:label` UrbanOnto
 - `rdfs:comment` [language: pl] Ontologia została stworzona na potrzeby projektu "Historical Ontology of Urban Space".
 - `rdfs:comment` [language: en] This ontology was developed in "Historical Ontology of Urban Space" project.
 - `skos:altLabel` [language: pl] ontologia przestrzeni miejskiej
 - `rdfs:seeAlso` <https://urbanonto.ihpan.edu.pl/>
 - `owl:versionInfo` [type: xsd:decimal] 1.0

Below the annotations, there are tabs for "Ontology imports", "Ontology Prefixes", and "General class axioms". The "Ontology imports" section is expanded, showing "Imported ontologies:" and "Direct Imports +":

- `<http://purl.org/bdot10k>`
 - `bdot10k`
 - Ontology IRI: `<https://purl.org/bdot10k>`
 - Location: <https://purl.org/bdot10k>
- `<http://purl.org/ontoghis>`
 - `ontoghis`
 - Ontology IRI: `<http://purl.org/ontoghis>`
 - Location: <http://purl.org/ontoghis>

Under "Indirect Imports", there is one entry:

- `<http://ontologies.makolab.com/oc/oc.ttl>`
 - `oc`
 - Ontology IRI: `<http://ontologies.makolab.com/oc/>`
 - Location: <http://ontologies.makolab.com/oc/oc.ttl>

III. 2 Dependencies of Urbanonto ontology

Where is it available?

The ontology is stored in a git repository available through Github at

<https://github.com/urbanonto>.

The Repository also provides the function of ontology version control. Subsequent versions are available as commits (revisions), see:

<https://github.com/UrbanOnto/urbanonto/commits>.

How to edit?

We recommend using [Protege](#) for ontology editing.

We expect that the following types of changes will be introduced to the ontology:

1. adding a new OWL class – mainly new types of topographic objects and their new functions
2. modifying an existing OWL class:
 - a. as concerns the logical description
 - b. as concerns annotations

The latter change type should comply with the conventions adopted upon the creation of the Urbanonto ontology.

Assumptions for Urbanonto ontology creation

Each class:

1. has a Polish name stored as an *rdfs:label* feature (with @pl tag) – this is the basic name for the given class
2. may have secondary names stored as *skos:altLabel* features (with tags appropriate for a given language, e.g. @de)
3. may have synonyms stored as *skos:hiddenLabel* features, with tags appropriate for a given language
4. should have a definition stored as an *rdfs:isDefinedBy* feature
 - a. Additional explanations for a given class should be entered as *rdfs:comment* features

The screenshot below provides an example of such a description:

The screenshot displays the Urbanonto ontology editor interface. The left pane shows a class hierarchy for 'fontanna wolnostojąca', including subclasses like 'altana', 'fontanna', and 'fontanna wolnostojąca'. The right pane shows the 'Annotations' for 'fontanna wolnostojąca', listing various properties and their values in different languages. Below the annotations is the 'Description' section, which includes an 'Equivalent To' section and a 'SubClass Of' section.

Annotations:

- rdfl:label [language: pl] fontanna wolnostojąca
- rdfl:comment [language: pl] Fontanny powstawały już w miastach starożytnych, ułatwiały mieszkańcom osiedli miejskich dostęp do wody pitnej. Mogą występować jako osobne obiekty (np. fontanna na środku rynku) albo być częścią kompozycyjną różnego rodzaju terenów ozdobnych, takich jak parki czy założenia zamkowe/dworskie/palacowe. Mogą być publiczne lub prywatne. Są też fontanny włączone do budynków, które choć postawione frontem do odbiorcy, stanowią raczej część budynku, aniżeli samodzielny obiekt usytuowany w przestrzeni.
- skos:altLabel [language: pl] wodotrysk
- skos:altLabel [language: en] artificial fountain
- skos:altLabel [language: en] fountain
- skos:altLabel [language: de] der Zierbrunnen
- skos:altLabel [language: fr] fontaine
- skos:altLabel [language: fr] jet d'eau
- skos:altLabel [language: de] der Springbrunnen
- skos:altLabel [language: ru] фонтан

Description: fontanna wolnostojąca

Equivalent To

- 'ma część' some basen
- 'ma funkcję niewłaściwą' value 'funkcja gospodarcza'
- 'ma funkcję niewłaściwą' value 'funkcja wypoczynkowa'
- 'ma funkcję właściwą' value 'funkcja estetyczna'
- fontanna

SubClass Of

- fontanna

General class axioms

III. 3 Example of correct class in the Urbanonto ontology

Database

The database of the Urbanonto System is managed with PostgreSQL, by means of the Postgis extension.

Host	hgis.ihpan.edu.pl
Port	5432
Name	house

Table 1 Parameters of database connection

The database contains information about specific topographic objects and manifestations of the following attributes of these objects:

1. name of object
2. location of object
3. function of object
4. type of object.

More information on the nature and functions of such manifestations is provided in [Methodology for building spatio-temporal databases of settlement development and territorial divisions](#).¹

Moreover, the database contains data on the mutual origin of objects.

Diagrams, tables, views, functions, sequences, and columns are described by means of comments in (English) intended to provide users with explanations about data entry and interpretation.

Column Name	#	Data type	Identity	Collation	Not Null
ABC imprecise_date	1	text		default	[v]
123 precise_date	2	int4			[v]

Ill. 4 Example of explanation provided in the form of a comment to the date_mappings table

¹ Cf. Kit Fine, *Things and Their Parts*, Midwest Studies in Philosophy, 23 (1):61-74 (1999).

Structure

The Urbanonto base is made up of two diagrams:

1. *ontology_sources*
2. *ontology*

The *ontology_sources* diagram includes the tables where "raw" data is entered. The *ontology* diagram covers tables, views, functions, etc. where "refined" data are presented.

The following data are "refined":

- location
- dates

Location data is "refined" by a cartographic expert who specifies the "raw" data entered into the *locations_raw* table in the three following tables:

1. *location_points_refined*
2. *location_lines_refined*
3. *locations_polygons_refined*

Data is automatically refined by remapping imprecise data as precise data in the *date_mappings* table.

Diagram of *ontology_sources*

III. 5 Tables of ontology_sources diagram

Monitoring views

The *ontology_sources* diagram offers four views for monitoring duplicated manifestations, *i.e.* periods when specific objects have more than one value per given property.

The duplicates identified in these views are not always errors, but database editors should review them.

The *quasi_types* view identifies topographic object types which have been recognised as significant for the data entered and which should form part of the ontology. These types are uploaded from the *new_type_name* column of the *topographic_object_type_manifestations* table, where we enter the types absent in the ontology.

Database design necessitates that all topographic types be registered in the *topographic_types* table, which means *i.a.* that each topographic type must have an *IRI* identifier, which should be defined in the ontology.

The *unrefined_locations* view presents the “raw” locations which have not been refined.

Irrespective of view type, the identified records should not be treated as error reports, but as suggestions to review the data entered.

Ontology diagram

In terms of structure, the tables of the *ontology* diagram are generally copies of the tables of the *ontology_sources* diagram – any differences stem from the above-described data refinement process and consistent use of identifiers in this last diagram.

III. 6 Tables of ontology diagram

Moreover, the *ontology* diagram contains four materialized views:

1. *topographic_object_function_manifestations_filled*
2. *topographic_object_location_manifestations_filled*
3. *topographic_object_name_manifestations_filled*
4. *topographic_object_type_manifestations_filled*

which contain “virtual” manifestations, *i.e.* manifestations of objects in periods for which source data has not been provided in appropriate aspects. Such “time gaps” are completed in full by a single manifestation whose value corresponds to the previous manifestation.

The *geonode_topographic_object_type_manifestations* view aggregates all the filled manifestations – this is the “final” view which presents data for the Geoserver application and for RDF Triple Store.

topographic_object_function_manifestations_filled	
123 identifier	int4
123 topographic_object_identifier	int4
🕒 start_at	date
🕒 end_at	date
123 function_identifier	int4
123 historical_evidence_identifier	int4

topographic_object_location_manifestations_filled	
123 identifier	int4
123 topographic_object_identifier	int4
🕒 start_at	date
🕒 end_at	date
123 location_identifier	int4
123 historical_evidence_identifier	int4
123 location_link_type_identifier	int4

topographic_object_name_manifestations_filled	
123 identifier	int4
123 topographic_object_identifier	int4
🕒 start_at	date
🕒 end_at	date
ABC name	text
123 historical_evidence_identifier	int4
123 name_link_type_identifier	int4

topographic_object_type_manifestations_filled	
123 identifier	int4
123 topographic_object_identifier	int4
🕒 start_at	date
🕒 end_at	date
123 type_identifier	int4
123 historical_evidence_identifier	int4

geonode_topographic_object_manifestations	
123 identifier	int4
123 topographic_object_identifier	int4
🕒 start_at	date
🕒 end_at	date
ABC function	text
📐 the_geom	geometry(geometry, 4326)
ABC name	text
ABC type	text
ABC function_iri	text
ABC type_iri	text

III. 7 Materialized views of ontology diagram

Administrative processes

How to add/change user access authorizations? How to create/delete users?

Start by assigning/revoking a role to/from a database user (creating/deleting users - standard PostgreSQL mechanisms):

- *house* for standard users
- *house_adm* for system administrator

Examples:

1. adding a user called *maniek*: `GRANT house TO maniek;`
2. deleting a user called *maniek*: `REVOKE house FROM maniek;`
3. granting administrator rights to user called *maniek*: `GRANT house_adm TO maniek;`
4. revoking administrator rights from user called *maniek*: `REVOKE house_adm FROM maniek;`

How to update data in the ontology diagram?

First, you need to log in as a *house* database user (or *postgres* user). Next, initiate the [ontology_sources2ontology.sql](#) script in the *house* database:

```
psql -f ontology_sources2ontology.sql house
```

How to protect the data?

A backup copy of the *house* database is automatically created daily at about 3:50 a.m. (*cron.daily*) by the `hgis.ihpan.edu.pl:/etc/cron.daily/HOUSE` script. Backup copy files are available at `hgis.ihpan.edu.pl:/var/backup/HOUSE/` (see verse 7 of the script).

Editing processes

Users should enter data ONLY to the tables in the diagram

The data in the *function* and *topographic_types* tables should come from the ontology – see section ‘How to synchronize the database with the ontology?’ below.

We recommend DBeaver (CE version) to enter data.

How to enter data?

The target data should be entered into one of the six tables describing changes to selected aspects of topographic objects:

1. *topographic_object_function_manifestations*
2. *topographic_object_location_manifestations*
3. *topographic_object_mereological_link_manifestations*
4. *topographic_object_name_manifestations*
5. *topographic_object_provenances*
6. *topographic_object_type_manifestations*

Owing to the dependencies between tables, entering data into these tables may require adding data in dependent tables. Table 2 presents the schematic sequence for entering data while taking into account these dependencies. Detailed dependencies have been presented in III. 5.

Sequence of data entry	Table	Comment
1	<i>date_mappings</i>	
1	<i>Functions</i>	data from ontology
1	<i>location_link_types</i>	
1	<i>location_lines_refined</i>	
1	<i>location_points_refined</i>	
1	<i>location_polygons_refined</i>	
1	<i>name_link_types</i>	
1	<i>location_datasets</i>	
1	<i>publication_sources</i>	
1	<i>topographic_objects</i>	
1	<i>topographic_types</i>	data from ontology
2	<i>historical_evidences</i>	
2	<i>locations_raw</i>	
2	<i>topographic_object_provenances</i>	
3	<i>topographic_object_function_manifestations</i>	
3	<i>topographic_object_location_manifestations</i>	
3	<i>topographic_object_name_manifestations</i>	
3	<i>topographic_object_type_manifestations</i>	
3	<i>topographic_object_mereological_link_manifestations</i>	

Table 2 Sequence of data entry in ontology_sources diagram – main dependencies

Example: How to enter data into the functions table?

III. 8 Dependencies in `topographic_object_function_manifestations` table

Column Name	#	Data type	Identity	Collation	Not Null	Default	Comment
<code>123 topographic_object_identifier</code>	1	int4			[v]		This column references to the object manifesting the function.
<code>ABC start_at</code>	2	text		default	[]		
<code>ABC end_at</code>	3	text		default	[]		
<code>ABC function</code>	4	text		default	[v]		
<code>123 identifier</code>	5	int4			[v]	nextva...	This identifies a manifestation.
<code>123 historical_evidence</code>	6	int4			[]		This column references to the evidence that supports the manifestation.
<code>ABC varia</code>	7	text		default	[]		This is an auxiliary column to provide the metadata useful for inputting data.

III. 9 Properties in `topographic_object_function_manifestations` table

As follows from the above diagrams, entering data into the `functions` table:

- requires the identifier of the object which a given function manifestation concerns
- requires the identifier of the function
- may require the identifier of the source of information about a given manifestation
- requires providing data on the manifestation start or end date, *i.e.* at least one of these dates.

For example, if one tries to enter the following record (III. 10: no. 3 and highlighted in green) to the `topographic_object_function_manifestations` table:

- a. 52.159446, 21.017488
- 5. Metadata:
 - a. Handke, K. (1998). Słownik nazewnictwa Warszawy. Warsaw, p. 175

Example of data entry – variable entity

In line with the dependencies presented in Ill. 5 (see above, page 10), let us start with entering the topographic object by adding a record to the *topographic_objects* table:²

id	identifier	default_name	author
2	nextval('ontology_sources.topographic_objects_seq':regclass)	ulica Puławska	PGA

Ill. 12 Example of variable topographic object – before database update

1. The *identifier* column is completed automatically.³
2. The *default_name* column contains a default name of a given object. This name is not processed and is used only to support the data editor.
3. The author column identifies the author of a given record. This identifier is not processed and is used only to support the data editor.

Upon entry, one should note the value of the generated object identifier. In this case, this value is 905.

² This is a variable object, which means that all of its attributes may change during its existence. Therefore the only 'information-giving' column of the *topographic_objects* table is the *identifier* column.

³ In principle, all record identifiers are unique only within one table.

Grid	123 identifier	ABC default_name	ABC author
863		865 Cerkiew św. Spirydona biskupa	OLP
864		866 Obelisk Aleksandra I	OLP
865		867 Fort Aleksieja	OLP
866		868 Fort Sergeja	OLP
867		869 Fort Władymira	OLP
868		870 Fort Georgija	OLP
869		871 Kościół bonifratrów	OLP
870		872 Brama Straceń Cytadeli Warszawskiej	OLP
871		873 Brama Nowomiejska Cytadeli Warszawskiej	OLP
872		874 Brama Powązkowska Cytadeli Warszawskiej	OLP
873		875 Brama Bielańska Cytadeli Warszawskiej	OLP
874		876 Ulica Konwiktorska	OLP
875		877 Ulica Muranowska	OLP
876		878 Plac Muranowski	OLP
877		879 Ulica Franciszkańska	OLP
878		880 Ulica Bonifratska	OLP
879		881 zespół klasztorny karmelitów bosych	KSZ
880		882 klasztor karmelitów bosych	KSZ
881		883 kościół Wniebowzięcia NMP i św. Józefa Oblubieńca	KSZ
882		884 Wyższe Metropolitalne Seminarium Duchowne	KSZ
883		885 brama do kościoła i klasztoru karmelitów bosych	KSZ
884		886 ogród przy klasztorze karmelitów bosych	KSZ
885		887 cmentarz przy klasztorze karmelitów bosych	KSZ
886		888 dzwonnica na cmentarzu przy klasztorze karmelitów bosych	KSZ
887		889 Kamienica Pleniszowska (hip. 366)	KSZ
888		890 zespół klasztorny bernardynów w Starej Warszawie	KSZ
889		891 kościół św. Anny	KSZ
890		892 klasztor bernardynów warszawskich	KSZ
891		893 cmentarz przy klasztorze bernardynów warszawskich	KSZ
892		894 dzwonnica kościoła św. Anny	KSZ
893		895 Kamienica (hip. 386)	KSZ
894		896 Ulica Bagno	OLP
895		897 Ulica Teodora	OLP
896		898 Ulica Chłodna	OLP
897		899 plac gen. H. Dąbrowskiego	OLP
898		900 ulica Graniczna	OLP
899		901 ulica Grzybowska	OLP
900		902 ulica Jasna	OLP
901		903 ulica Hoża	OLP
902		904 ulica Kredytowa	OLP
903		905 ulica Puławska	PGA

III. 13 Example of variable topographic object – after database update

The next step is to enter information about the historical source.

Example of entering data – changes in type

The historical sources which provide confirmation of the data entered can be found in the **historical_evidences** table. In this case, it is not necessary to enter a new source, as the source concerned has already been entered under identifier 95:

Grid	123 identifier	ABC page_from	ABC page_to	ABC publication_identifier
94	95	175	175	#Handke_1998

III. 14 Example of registered historical source

Next, we can enter descriptions of changes by type, in any order.

Example of entering data – changes in type

Changes in type should be introduced to the *topographic_object_type_manifestations* table.

Let us attempt to enter the following information: object 905 has been a street from 1917 to the present day (the year 2000 in the database).

topographic_object_id	start_at	end_at	type	identifier	historical_evidence	source	new_type_name
2	1526.0	1839.0	budynek gospodarczy	2	1	[NULL]	[NULL]
3	1356.0	1864.0	zespół sakralny lub klasztorny	3	3	[NULL]	[NULL]
4	905	1917	ulica	4	3	[NULL]	[NULL]

Ill. 15 Example of successfully entered topographic object type manifestation.

1. We enter the registered identifier of the object whose type we are specifying (905 in this case) into the *topographic_object_identifier* column.
2. The dates marking the period when object 905 was a street should be entered into the *start_at* and *end_at* columns.
3. Enter object type, i.e. street, into the *type* column.⁴
 - a. It is necessary to pre-define the entered type in the ontology and to register the type in the *topographic_types* table.
4. The *identifier* column is completed automatically.
5. Enter the historical source identifier, in this case 95, into the *historical_evidence* column.

At this point, let us make an attempt at entering the following information: from 1825 to 1916 object 905 was a tract.

topographic_object_id	start_at	end_at	type	identifier	historical_evidence	source	new_type_name
1	1379.0	1560.0	baszta	1	1	[NULL]	[NULL]
2	905	1825	trakt	2	95	[NULL]	[NULL]
3	1526.0	1839.0	budynek gospodarczy	3	2	[NULL]	[NULL]
4	1356.0	1864.0	zespół sakralny lub klasztorny	4	3	[NULL]	[NULL]
5	1356.0	1400.0	kościół	5	3	[NULL]	kościół
6	1356.0	1441.0	klasztor	6	3	[NULL]	[NULL]
7	1356.0	[NULL]	cmentarz	7	3	[NULL]	[NULL]
8	1400.0	1944.0	kościół	8	3	[NULL]	kościół
9	1441.0	1864.0	klasztor	9	3	[NULL]	[NULL]
10	1650.0	1864.0	klasztor	10	3	[NULL]	[NULL]

Data error

Error synchronizing data with database

Reason:
SQL Error [23503]: BŁĄD: wstawianie lub modyfikacja na tabeli "topographic_object_type_manifestations" narusza klucz obcy "topographic_object_type_manifestation_sources_types_fkey"
Szczegóły: Klucz (type)=(trakt) nie występuje w tabeli "topographic_types".

Details >> OK

Ill. 16 Example of failed attempt to enter topographic object type manifestation.

The system prevented the entry of data, because the *topographic_types* table does not contain a type called tract. In such situations, it is necessary to pre-modify the ontology by adding a new type.

A similar situation occurs for the information that object 905 has been a street from 1917 to the present day ("2000" in database).

⁴ More precisely, input the type label (*rdfs:label*).

Example of entering data – changes in location

In order to enter changes in location, we need to start by completing the *locations_raw* table with a verse corresponding to the 52.159446, 21.017488 location:

id	identifier	the_geom_text	name	location_dataset_identifier	variable	historical_evidence	location_link_type	date_range	change	type_identifier
2	ontology_sour	52.159446, 21.017488	[NULL]	[NULL]	[NULL]	95	dokladnie	[NULL]	[NULL]	[NULL]

Ill. 17 Example of entering “raw” location to *locations_raw* table

When entering records into the *locations_raw* table, we only need to complete the following columns:

1. *the_geom_text* – entering data into *the_geom_text* will automatically complete *the_geom* column, which stores actual object location.
2. The *identifier* column is completed automatically.

When entering records into the *locations_raw* table, we *should* complete the following columns:

1. *historical_evidence*

At this point, when entering records into the *locations_raw* table it is *not possible* to complete the following columns:

1. *location_point_refined_identifier*
2. *location_line_refined_identifier*
3. *location_polygon_refined_identifier*

We will complete these columns after finishing the process of refining the geographical data. The remaining columns of the *locations_raw* table are auxiliary columns and their completion is optional.

After entering data into the *locations_raw* table, we should take note of the generated identifier. In our example, this identifier is 926.

The design of the database provides two options in the next step:

1. refining geographical data
2. adding a location manifestation

Example of entering data – changes in location – refining geographical data

The data refinement process is most frequently initiated in the tool for editing geographical data, e.g. QGIS. First, you need to provide the PostgreSQL data source:

The data refinement process ends with entering the refined data into one of the following tables:

1. *location_point_refined_identifier*
2. *location_line_refined_identifier*
3. *location_polygon_refined_identifier*

The table selected should correspond to the outcome of the refinement process, e.g. whether the obtained geographical data corresponds to a point, a line, or a polygon.

Next, we enter the generated identifier into the appropriate column of the

`locations_raw` table

In this case, this is the `location_line_refined_identifier` column.

Example of entering data – changes in location – adding location manifestation

Changes in location should be introduced to the

`topographic_object_location_manifestations` table:

	123 topographic_object_identifier	asc start_at	asc end_at	asc location_link_type	123 identifier	123 location_identifier	123 historical_evidence	asc varia
2	905	[NULL]	2000	dokladnie	ology_sources.to	926	95	[NULL]

1. We enter the registered identifier of the topographic object whose location we are specifying (905 in this case) into the `topographic_object_identifier` column.
2. We enter the dates into the `start_at` and `end_at` columns to define the period when object 905 was situated in the given location.
3. We enter the identifier of the unrefined manifestation, *i.e.* identifier generated in the `locations_raw` (926) table, into the `location_idenfifer` column.
4. `location_link_type`
 - a. The used location type must be pre-registered in the `location_link_types` table.
5. The `identifier` column is completed automatically.
6. Enter the historical source identifier, in this case 95, into the `historical_evidence` column.

id	name
1	dokładnie
2	przybliżona
3	prawdopodobna
4	obok
5	obok prawdopodobna
6	dookoła
7	dookoła prawdopodobnie
8	między
9	między prawdopodobnie
10	wśród
11	wśród prawdopodobnie
12	wzdłuż
13	wzdłuż prawdopodobnie
14	w poprzek
15	w poprzek prawdopodobnie
16	nad
17	nad prawdopodobnie
18	pod
19	pod prawdopodobnie
20	za
21	za prawdopodobnie
22	przed
23	przed prawdopodobnie
24	na lewo od
25	na prawo od
26	na północ od
27	na południe od
28	na wschód od
29	na zachód od
30	na północny wschód od
31	na północny zachód od
32	na południowy wschód od
33	na południowy zachód od

Ill. 18 Exemplary content of location_link_types table

Example of entering data – changes in name

Changes in name should be introduced to the *topographic_object_name_manifestations*.

In this example we want to enter “tract to Nowa Aleksandria” as the name for our object bearing identifier 905, and provide information that this was the basic name for this object between 1825 and 1916.

id	topographic_object_identifier	start_at	end_at	name	name_link_type	identifier	historical_evidence	varia
1	1	1379.0	1560.0	Baszta Biała	nazwa podstawowa	7,256	[NULL]	[NULL]
2	905	1825	1916	trakt Nowoaleksandryjski	nazwa podstawowa	ology_sources.to	95	[NULL]

Ill. 19 Example of name entry

1. Enter the registered identifier of the object concerned into the *topographic_object_identifier* column.
2. We enter the dates into the *start_at* and *end_at* columns to define the period when the given name was used for object 905.

3. Enter the name, i.e. “tract to Nowa Aleksandria” (without quotation marks) into the name column.
4. The *identifier* column is completed automatically.
5. Enter the historical source identifier, in this case 95, into the *historical_evidence* column.
6. Enter the name type, i.e. “basic name” (without quotation marks) into the column.
 - a. The used name type must be pre-registered in the *name_link_types* table.

id	name
1	nazwa podstawowa
2	nazwa oboczna

III. 20 Exemplary content of *name_link_types* table

Similarly, we enter the two other names for object 905.

Where not to enter data?

1. Do NOT enter data to the tables of the *ontology* diagram.
2. Do NOT enter non-ontology data to the *functions* and *topographic_types* tables.

How to synchronize the database with the ontology?

The database is synchronised in terms of topographic object types (*topographic_types* table) and functions (*functions* table).

This synchronization can be performed manually or by initiating the [python script ontology_sources2ontology.sql](#). The automatic script updates both tables by adding new ontological objects, but it does not delete objects which have been deleted from the ontology.

Data deletion process

In order to delete data, one ought to perform the data entry process in reverse, i.e. start with the manifestations table.

Data access process

Data from the *house* database are available:

1. via Geoserver, as OGC standard services
2. as RDF Triple, via SPARQL endpoint

GeoNode/GeoServer

For project purposes, a GeoNode instance has been initiated:

- as a light-weight namespace container (systemd-nspawn); operation:
 - `sudo systemctl start systemd-nspawn@data.service` :- initiation
 - `sudo systemctl stop systemd-nspawn@data.service` :- stopping
- GeoNode URL= <https://data.atlasfontium.pl/>
- GeoServer URL= <https://data.atlasfontium.pl/geoserver/>
- authentication integrated with the LDAP IHPAN authentication system

On a test basis, we published the 'geonode_topographic_object_manifestations' layer:

https://data.atlasfontium.pl/layers/ontology:geonode:geonode_topographic_object_manifestations

WFS URL (GeoJSON) =

https://data.atlasfontium.pl/geoserver/ows?service=WFS&version=1.0.0&request=GetFeature&typename=geonode%3Ageonode_topographic_object_manifestations&outputFormat=json&srs=EPSG%3A4326&srsName=EPSG%3A4326

Procedure for layer publication in GeoNode:

1. Go to GeoServer to add a new store (<https://data.atlasfontium.pl/geoserver/web/wicket/bookmarkable/org.geoserver.web.data.store.NewDataPage>) - Vector 'PostGIS' data source with the following parameters:

PostGIS
PostGIS Database

Basic Store Info

Obszar roboczy *

geonode ▼

Nazwa źródła danych *

ontology

Opis

Systemy Urbanonto

Włączone

Connection Parameters

host *

postgres

port *

5432

database

house

schema

ontology

user *

datafontium

passwd

.....

Namespace *

http://www.geonode.org/

Expose primary keys

max connections

10

min connections

1

fetch size

1000

Batch insert size

1

- Click on 'Publish', the button next to the name of the added 'geonode_topographic_object_manifestations' layer:

New Layer

Add a new layer

You can create a new feature type by manually configuring the attribute names and types. [Create new feature type...](#)
On databases you can also create a new feature type by configuring a native SQL statement. [Configure new SQL view...](#)
Tu znajduje się lista zasobów w składnicy: 'ontology'. Naciśnij na warstwę, którą chcesz konfigurować

Published	Layer name	Action
	functions	Publish
	geonode_topographic_object_manifestations	Publish
	gt_pk_metadata	Publish
	historical_evidences	Publish
	location_datasets	Publish
	location_link_types	Publish
	locations	Publish
	name_link_types	Publish
	publication_sources	Publish
	topographic_object_function_manifestations	Publish
	topographic_object_function_manifestations_filled	Publish
	topographic_object_location_manifestations	Publish
	topographic_object_location_manifestations_filled	Publish
	topographic_object_manifestations	Publish
	topographic_object_manifestations_with_iris	Publish
	topographic_object_mereological_link_manifestations	Publish
	topographic_object_name_manifestations	Publish
	topographic_object_name_manifestations_filled	Publish
	topographic_object_provenances	Publish
	topographic_object_type_manifestations	Publish
	topographic_object_type_manifestations_filled	Publish
	topographic_objects	Publish
	topographic_types	Publish

3. Set standard options -

Edit Layer

Edit layer data and publishing

[geonode:geonode_topographic_object_manifestations](#)

Configure the resource and publishing information for the current layer

Dane Publishing Dimensions Dynamic dim. defaults Buforowanie Kafelków

Edit Layer

Podstawowe informacje o zasobie

Nazwa

geonode_topographic_object_manifestations

- Włączone
- Advertised

Tytuł

geonode_topographic_object_manifestations

Abstract

Keywords

Aktualne Słowa Kluczowe

features
geonode_topographic_object_manifestations Usuń zaznaczony

New Keyword

Słownictwo

Add Keyword

Linki metadanych

No metadata links so far

Dodaj łącze *Zwróć uwagę, że tylko metadane FGDC i TC211 pokazywane są w możliwościach WMS 1.1.1*

Data links

No data links so far

Dodaj łącze

Referencyjny układ współrzędnych

Natywna SRS

EPSG:4326 EPSG:WGS 84...

Deklarowana SRS

EPSG:4326 Znajdź... EPSG:WGS 84...

Obsługa SRS

Wymuszono Deklaracje

Granice

Natywna granica

Min X	Min Y	Max X	Max Y

[Obliczyć na podstawie danych](#)

Compute from SRS bounds

Szerokość/Długość geograficzna granicy

Min X	Min Y	Max X	Max Y

[Oblicz na podstawie natywnych granic](#)

Curved geometries control

Linear geometries can contain circular arcs

Linearization tolerance (useful only if your data contains curved geometries)

Szczegóły Typów Usługi

Właściwość	Typ	Możliwy brak wartości	Min/Max wystąpień
identifier	Integer	true	0/1
topographic_object_identifier	Integer	true	0/1
start_at	Date	true	0/1
end_at	Date	true	0/1
function	String	true	0/1
the_geom	Geometry	true	0/1
name	String	true	0/1
type	String	true	0/1
function_iri	String	true	0/1
type_iri	String	true	0/1

Załaduj ponownie typ obiektu ⚠ ...

- in particular in the 'Native border' field - click on 'Calculate based on data'. In 'Geographical Width/Length of Border' click on 'Calculate based on native borders':

Referencyjny układ współrzędnych

Natywna SRS
 [EPSG:WGS 84...](#)

Deklarowana SRS
 [EPSG:WGS 84...](#)

Obsługa SRS

Granice

Natywna granica

Min X	Min Y	Max X	Max Y
20.963768005371	52.2065124511715	21.052013397216	52.276195526123

[Obliczyć na podstawie danych](#)
[Compute from SRS bounds](#)

Szerokość/Długość geograficzna granicy

Min X	Min Y	Max X	Max Y
20.963768005371	52.2065124511715	21.052013397216	52.276195526123

[Oblicz na podstawie natywnych granic](#)

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function	String	true	0/1
the_geom	Geometry	true	0/1
name	String	true	0/1
type	String	true	0/1
function_iri	String	true	0/1
type_iri	String	true	0/1

[Załaduj ponownie typ obiektu](#) ⚠️ ...

- When publishing the test version, it proved necessary to introduce the following change: 'Publishing' tab, 'WMS Settings' are, 'Default style' field: change to 'polygon' (the default style caused the GeoServer to generate an error in the logs: *java.lang.RuntimeException: org.xml.sax.SAXParseException; Premature end of file*).
- Go to GeoNode to update information on the layers present in the store=*ontology*: log in (via ssh) as *geonode* user to data.atlasfontium.pl and run the command:
`geonode updatelayers -s ontology`

Command result:

```
Inspecting the available layers in GeoServer ...
Found 1 layers, starting processing
[created] Layer geonode_topographic_object_manifestations (1/1)
```

Finished processing 1 layers in 12.78 seconds.

1 Created layers
0 Updated layers

0 Failed layers
12.78 seconds per layer

After the last command is executed, the following layer will be added to GeoNode:

The screenshot shows a web browser window displaying a GeoNode layer page. The URL is https://data.atlasfontium.pl/layers/ontology:geonode:geonode_topographic_object_manifestations. The page title is "geonode_topographic_object_manifestations".

The main content area features a map of a city area with a gray polygon overlay. Below the map are several tabs: "Informacje", "Atrybuty", "Udostępny", "Oceny", and "Komentarze".

The "Informacje" tab is active, showing the following details:

- Tytuł:** geonode_topographic_object_manifestations
- Licencja:** Not Specified
- Streszczenie:** No abstract provided
- Publication Date:** 15 września 2021 16:42
- Typ:** Vector Data
- Słowa kluczowe:**
 - features
 - geonode_topographic_object_manifestations
- Regiony:** Global
- Osoba odpowiedzialna:** admin

On the right side of the page, there are several sections:

- Buttons:** "Pobierz warstwę", "Szczegóły metadanych", "Zobacz warstwę", "Pobierz metadane".
- Legenda:** Default Polygon, Gray Polygon with Black Outline.
- Mapy korzystające z tej warstwy:** Ta warstwa nie jest obecnie używana w żadnej z map.
- Style:** Następujące style są związane z tą warstwą. Wybierz styl, żeby go zobaczyć na podglądzie. (styl domyślny) Default Polygon.
- O serwisie:** Osoba odpowiedzialna, osoba kontaktowa, autor metadanych. admin, Brak grupy.

RDF Triple Store

Data from the database are available as RDF Triples stored in triple store ([Fuseki](#) technology) via the SPARQL endpoint = <https://urbanonto.ihpan.edu.pl/sparql> (demo: <https://urbanonto.ihpan.edu.pl/endpoint/>).

Creating a triplestore instance:

1. create an *urbanfuseki* user: `sudo useradd -c urbanFuseki -d /var/lib/urbanfuseki -M -r -s /sbin/nologin urbanfuseki`
2. delete home directory of user: `sudo rm -rf /var/lib/urbanfuseki`
3. create home directory of user: `sudo install -d -o root -g root -m0755 /var/lib/urbanfuseki`
4. place script in home directory of user: `sudo install -o root -g root -m0755 urbanfuseki.sh /var/lib/urbanfuseki/urbanfuseki.sh`
5. initiate script as root: `sudo /var/lib/urbanfuseki/urbanfuseki.sh`
6. initiate service: `sudo systemctl start urbanfuseki.service`

The script collects and configures all necessary service elements. Among others, it adds the *urbanfuseki* service (*/etc/systemd/system/urbanfuseki.servicefile*) and creates the */var/lib/urbanfuseki/urbanonto.ttl* file which contains RDF triples = data from the database.

Manual update of the file: */var/lib/urbanfuseki/urbanonto.ttl*: `sudo /var/lib/urbanfuseki/urbanfuseki.sh`

Should any problems occur while using the service (does not open, does not operate correctly), repeat the whole procedure of creating a triplestore instance.

IMPORTANT: set the right variable values at the beginning of the script (already set on the *hgis.ihpan.edu.pl* host):

- `jdbcDSN=jdbc:postgresql://<USER>:<PASS>@<HOST>:<PORT>/${DBS}`
- `MAP_URL="https://raw.githubusercontent.com/UrbanOnto/urbanonto/master/database/scripts/d2rq_mapping_urbanonto.ttl"`

RDF triples are generated daily at about 3:50 a.m. (*cron.daily*) – the *hgis.ihpan.edu.pl:/var/lib/urbanfuseki/urbanfuseki.sh* script which updates the contents of the */var/lib/urbanfuseki/urbanonto.ttl* file is launched in *hgis.ihpan.edu.pl:/etc/cron.daily/HOUSE*. The script uses [D2RQ](#) mapping.

Technology used (stack)

Programming languages

Python

Database management systems

PostgreSQL (with PostGIS extension)

Applications

Protégé

DBeaver

GeoNode

D2RQ

Fuseki

Git

QGIS or other tool for geographic data editing